

A CHALLENGING FUTURE FOR IMPROVED PHOTOVOLTAIC SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Silicon photovoltaic arrays have been the workhorse power supplier to satellites since the beginning of the U.S. Space program. Through evolutionary improvement they still retain that title, although a few newcomers led by gallium-arsenide are forging paths into the silicon kingdom. Concurrent with the changes in photovoltaic technology, the satellite market has swept into broad new horizons. Satellite payloads now range from commercial communications antennas to early warning sensors. Bold new systems such as directed energy weapons and global cellular telephone coverage are being developed. Meanwhile, the nation's braintrust is formulating plans to send men to Mars. The expansion of space requirements creates new opportunities and priorities for power production, thus driving the development of innovative technologies.

Introduction

Photovoltaic technology has evolved significantly over the history of the U.S. Space program. This evolution has resulted in better performing solar arrays which have enabled an ever-growing span of space missions. Many factors will influence the development of new photovoltaic systems. In addition to traditional satellite functions like communications and weather monitoring, new and expanded space missions are emerging. These include a missile tracking and interceptor systems being developed by the Strategic Defense Initiative Organization, the Space Exploration Initiative in NASA, and direct broadcast television systems in the commercial sector.

In addition to broadening space missions, several other factors will influence the research and development community. Increased emphasis on nuclear systems development may produce viable competitive to solar for some missions. The opening of the international market place is another competition factor. Tightening federal budgets will place emphasis on affordability and lifetime of solar arrays. Meanwhile, the proliferation of small satellites will require more emphasis on produceability. The far-reaching changes taking place in the Soviet Union may decrease emphasis on survivability, especially to exotic hostile threats. Emphasis on minimum weight may decrease as larger and less costly launch vehicles are developed.

When looking at a composite view of the broadening market, increasing competition, evolving requirements, and decreasing government budgets; it is clear that the crystal ball shows a very challenging future for the photovoltaics industry. To fill this need, innovative concepts will be required at both

the cell and array level. Creativity will also be key to establishing ways to accelerate the process of transitioning new technologies from the laboratory to the marketplace.

KEY REQUIREMENTS

Cell Efficiency

In recent history, improving photovoltaics has been synonymous with increasing cell efficiency. However, this has directly resulted in many ideas which never made it to production and others like gallium-arsenide which have been slower to transition than most experts anticipated. The problem is that efficiency is not an end in itself, but a means to an end. Ideally, higher efficiencies lead to arrays which are smaller, lighter, and less costly. However, if efficiency increases are achieved by using heavy and/or expensive materials, two of these goals will not be reached. This results in a much smaller market since few satellite programs will risk using an emerging technology only for reduced array area. Another illustration of this point is the growing interest in amorphous silicon arrays for satellites. Although significantly less efficient than the alternatives, amorphous silicon potentially offers low weight and very low recurring cost. Thus, factors other than efficiency should drive the development of new technologies. While increased efficiency may be a way to achieve other goals, it is those goals that must be used to evaluate alternatives.

Specific Power

While high specific power will always be an important parameter for satellite solar arrays, the emphasis on weight as the single critical factor in array design and selection is going away. The reason for emphasis on weight historically has been due to limiting restrictions on satellite mass from the U.S. family of launch vehicles and the cost of putting satellites into orbit.

Significant increases in payload mass which can be put into orbit are being achieved through upgrades to the Titan IV and development of a new National Launch System (NLS). Mass capabilities of the Medium Launch Vehicle systems are also being increased. This reduces the importance on satellite component weights because that is no longer a factor in the feasibility of most missions. With the 150,000 pound payload capability of the NLS, most currently envisioned missions have substantial weight margins before feasibility becomes an issue.

The NLS program will also provide a family of launch vehicles which substantially reduce the cost per pound of launching satellites. The emphasis on weight then becomes a different kind of cost issue. If a lighter solar array, when

added to weight savings possible with other components, makes it possible to use a smaller launch vehicle, then the lighter array may be used even if it is more expensive.

While the importance of specific power is decreasing, it is still an important factor. Even though launch costs will be reduced, they will still be high enough to be an important factor in satellite component design. Another important point here is that weight must be optimized at the system level, not at the array level. For example, a heavier solar array may be the best option for a low orbit satellite if it has a smaller area, and thus reduces drag and therefore the amount of drag makeup propellant required.

Packaging

The stowed volume and footprint of an array is another important factor. Innovative concepts which can be stowed in unusually shaped volumes or which greatly decrease stowed volume may find many applications. This is because special purpose satellites must be designed to fit into standard launch vehicle shrouds. This match is not always simple and often results in wasted space in the shroud and sometimes requires a larger and more expensive launch vehicle. Thus, smaller stowed arrays or arrays which can be conformably packaged will get a lot of interest from satellite builders.

Affordability

While affordability has always been a key driver for solar array development and design, the emphasis on low cost is increasing. In some cases, the solar array is the single most expensive subsystem on a satellite. Combine this with trends to both bigger satellites with higher power requirements and to large constellations of small satellites, and array cost may become the driving concern for many applications. As power levels increase, more consideration is given to comparing photovoltaic arrays with other power sources such as nuclear reactors or solar dynamic systems. As an example, the recurring cost of a solar dynamic system for Space Station Freedom would be less than half that of a photovoltaic system.

On small satellites, the solar array cost becomes a larger percentage of satellite cost than on large satellites. This is because many aspects of the solar array cost do not scale linearly with size (such as the gimbal). When considering constellations of tens of hundreds of satellites like SDIO's Brilliant Eyes and Brilliant Pebbles program, array cost becomes a significant part of the system cost. Thus cost is a very major factor in array selection and design for these systems.

While it does not make sense to do extensive cost estimations early in the development of array components, it is important to keep major cost drivers in mind. For example, materials which are rare and/or inherently expensive should be avoided and the number of processing steps should be minimized.

Reliability/Lifetime

If affordability is a major driver in the satellite business, then it follows that lifetime is just as important. This is because the life cycle cost of a satellite system is directly related to satellite lifetime. For example, if satellites need to be replaced every twelve years instead of ten years for a system, the savings to the program is nearly twenty percent.

While solar arrays do not typically limit satellite life, the degradation rate of the solar cells does effect array size and cost. Reliability is also a critical part of lifetime estimates. The most likely part of the array to fail is the development system. Although rare, a solar array which fails to deploy renders a satellite useless. Recent developments such as retractable arrays have improved this array feature, but improvements in this area are still important.

THE COMPETITION

New photovoltaic concepts will meet stiff competition before they can enter the marketplace on anything more than an experimental basis. The stiffest challenge is always from traditional concepts like rigid silicon arrays. This is because they are proven systems which can be used with high levels of confidence. Also, the established market base provides a continuing business with its inherent cost advantages. Other competitors include other new photovoltaic concepts, solar dynamic systems, nuclear reactors and radioisotope generators (RTGs), and innovative new ideas.

Photovoltaic Concepts

Many new concepts are being developed for advanced power systems. These include high efficiency cells such as multi-band gap concepts, radiation resistant cells like copper-indium-diselenide, very thin film concepts such as cleft gallium-arsenide, and concentrator array ideas led by the Survivable Low Appature Trough System (SLATS) concept, ~~nozzle~~ substrates, deployment systems and materials are also critical deployment items. Another key to the competitiveness of photovoltaic systems is the advances being made in spacecraft batteries. Efforts on nickel-hydrogen, sodium-sulfur, and rechargeable lithium batteries are providing the basis for improvements in lifetime, weight and cost of the energy storage portion of a photovoltaic power system.

Solar Dynamics

These systems use a large dish concentrator to focus the sun's energy onto a heat receiver. The heat is then used in one of several thermodynamic cycles to generate electricity. A thermal energy storage medium provides heat for use in eclipse. Options for the operating cycle include Brayton, Rankine, and Stirling. These systems have several potential disadvantages. Because they use rotating machinery, reliability as well as vibration and torque transmitted to the satellite are concerns. Dynamic systems also do not scale down well, and are only serious competitors in the range of tens of kilowatts. Their potential for high efficiency does make them size and weight competitive with advanced photovoltaic concepts and they have the potential to be very low cost power sources.

Nuclear

Nuclear systems also must seriously be considered as competition to photovoltaic power systems. RTGs have long been used for interplanetary missions. Although safety concerns limit their use in earth orbit, RTGs offer long life, high reliability, and excellent performance to small satellites.

For larger systems, space nuclear reactors are being developed which will provide keen competition. The U.S. is leveraging the demonstrated Soviet Union expertise in thermionic based reactors by purchasing and testing a Soviet Topaz II reactor. This system has flight heritage and delivers 6

kilowatts in a 1000 kilogram package which is also inexpensive. The SP-100 program, co-sponsored by NASA, DoD, and DOE, is developing lightweight, inexpensive reactor technology based on thermoelectric converters. Potential drawbacks to the nuclear systems include safety, lifetime and reliability concerns. Development costs are high for these systems, but demand is growing due to their very attractive potential for low recurring cost and low weight, especially at higher power levels. It should be noted for most applications nuclear power sources would not be used, unless there were no acceptable alternatives, because of safety considerations.

INNOVATION

New ideas are the key to continued vitality of any industry, and photovoltaics is no exception. The space market is expanding both in terms of the variety of missions and the numbers of projected satellites. Solar arrays traditionally are 10 to 20 percent of satellite weight and 10 to 30 percent of satellite cost. Therefore, continued improvement of photovoltaic arrays is critical to our progress in the space area. In a technology as mature as photovoltaics, innovation requires a significant effort. While evolutionary improvements to business as usual is the norm, revolutionary advancements require a different perspective. A good example is the capacitor industry which was characterized by slow evolutionary growth until the last ten years. Then SDI requirements for orders of magnitude improvements resulted in different approaches such as specially formulated new materials which has met these requirements.

Innovation, however, must not be limited to just the product. Innovation in the development process is also important. This is especially true in the technology transition process. Photovoltaics is an industry with a history of slow to no transition of revolutionary ideas. Some improvements such as increasing flight test opportunities are being implemented, but more is needed. A critical part of this must be increased involvement of the satellite community in the development of photovoltaics. Because of their integrated system experience, they can be very valuable in helping to set the right path early in the development process.